

CRDC DATA WORKFLOW END-TO-END ANALYSIS

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1. Background

The Cancer Research Data Commons (CRDC) is an audacious and ambitious NCI plan to integrate federated sources of cancer data, including clinical, genomic, proteomic, imaging, and canine, among others. Ultimately, the CRDC will be the repository for all information relating to patients and research subjects with cancer. This

will be a transformative repository of data, allowing researchers access to an enormous array of data across many disparate types.

In the years since the CRDC was conceived, several repositories of cancer data have been developed and have since evolved. These include data type-specific repositories such as the Genomic Data Commons (GDC), the Imaging Data Commons (IDC), the Proteomic Data Commons (PDC), and other domain specific data repositories such as the Integrated Canine Data Commons (ICDC), the Clinical Trials Data Commons (CTDC), the Cancer Data Service (CDS), and the Human Tissue Atlas Network (HTAN). Other initiatives, such as the Gabriella Miller Kids First Data Resource Center (GMKF), house data that will need to be connected to data sources across the CRDC. In addition, three groups have designed and deployed the [Cancer Cloud Resources](#) - Seven Bridges Genomics, the Broad Institute, and the Institute for Systems Biology (ISB). These latter programs create analytical frameworks for multi-modal data, and also utilize data integration and classification strategies to help realize their goals.

While some central guidance has been provided by NCI, each group has developed their own approaches to various aspects of the data life cycle. As outlined below, this includes every aspect of data management, from the time of data preparation and submission up until the data are subject to analysis and/or provided to researchers.

Figure 1. Typical data lifecycle management stages.

The purpose of this report is to describe community best practices for data life cycle management (**Fig. 1**). While we have also enumerated the opportunities available to each node or data provider to adopt these methodologies in a separate report submitted to NCI/CRDC, recommendations have been redacted from this summary. It is hoped that by adhering more closely to FAIR-compliant common standards for the various aspects of data management, the CRDC will be better able to more effectively and efficiently consume, store, share, and analyze data to realize cancer advancements and improve patients' lives. Ultimately, the goal is for the CRDC to have the capability of handling complex data requests that require querying across multiple nodes and data resources - and this cannot happen without some harmonization of efforts across the ecosystem.

The format for this report describes the data life cycle components, with specific examples of best practices. Where possible, the approach used by each node will be highlighted

It is important to note that by the very nature of this field and the fast-moving landscape of the CRDC, **this report will be out-of-date on the day it is published!** However, we envision that this document can be updated as each node and data provider adopt new data standards and evolve their data life cycle management practices.

1.1 Target Audience

There are several stakeholders that will benefit from this report:

- **NCI leadership:** Ultimately, the recommendations laid out here for the CRDC are likely also applicable across a broader reaching suite of NCI and ultimately NIH activities and programs. The authority of NCI leadership to endorse some or all of the recommendations and help lead the realization of the goals will be pivotal to successful adoption and deployment.
- **CRDC leadership:** The individuals who are leading the various efforts across the ecosystem will benefit from seeing descriptions of how the various nodes and data resources are approaching data life cycle management. It is hoped that based on this report, there will be opportunities for CRDC leadership to align on principles and practices across the CRDC.
- **Nodes and data resource stakeholders:** A primary audience for this report will be the individuals leading efforts for the nodes and data resources. It will be helpful for these groups to see how each node and data resource is approaching the various aspects of the data life cycle. It would be a great outcome, if this report resulted in an ongoing productive dialog between the nodes/data resources.
- **CCDH and CDA collaboration:** As the two primary groups that support harmonization efforts across the CRDC ecosystem, feedback from the CRDC community and NCI leadership on this report will be critical for planning and realizing CCDH and CDA future priorities and goals.
- **Other NCI Programs:** The interests of CCDH significantly intersect other programs supported by parts of NCI/CBIIT, the semantic engineering team at NCI. These findings and recommendations will likely present themselves as useful to other programs within NCI that rely on such engineering, for example the Childhood Cancer Data Initiative (CCDI). Ultimately, CCDI should be creating data resources (e.g., National Childhood Cancer Registry (NCCR)) that will become part of the overall CRDC.

1.2 Scope

This analysis is restricted to describing the data flow and life cycle for the CRDC nodes and CRDC Cloud Data Resources. This includes (1) submission of data to the nodes, (2) quality assurance and quality control, (3) annotation, (4) modeling, (5) mapping and transformation of data, (6) data integration, (7) data query and analysis, and (8) dissemination. Activities outside of this lifecycle are beyond the scope of this report; for example, tools and resources for researchers to prepare their data for submission or how data are used once delivered to the researcher are beyond the scope of this report.

2. Node Observations

The following are summaries of findings across the nodes. The figure below (**Fig. 2**) shows the journey that data undergo before ingestion into CRDC resources, within the respective CRDC component, and as they are made available to the public. Detailed notes and analysis can be found in the Appendices sections below.

Figure 2. The data lifecycle at CRDC, from Submission to Analysis.

2.1 Data submission

Data will enter the CRDC through various channels. In the simplest scenario, a researcher will submit a single set of data with a limited number of data types. For instance, an oncologist that has genomic data on 50 patients with breast cancer, along with a set of limited clinical data and outcomes. In this case, the user would work with the CDS or the GDC to arrange data submission. More complex submissions will need to be considered. For instance, the same oncologist may want to submit histology slides and biospecimens for the same 50 patients. In this case, it will be critical to be able to link across data types with an identifier. Further, it will be useful to facilitate updates to data and outcomes through an identifier that maps to an honest broker at the originating institution. But in either scenario, the onus is mostly on the investigator to prepare the data in a form and format that can be consumed by the node or data resource with minimal transformation. (**Fig. 3**)

Ingesting from other repositories. In certain cases, nodes may consume data from sources other than end-users / researchers. For instance, the IDC consumes data from the Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA), which provides DICOM-standardized images via an API. Submitters to the TCIA include HTAN and the ICDC, among others. CPTAC supplies data for the PDC, and the CTDC receives clinical trials directly from the MATCH-BOX system, part of the NCI MATCH. In all of these cases, there are opportunities for coordination and harmonization of processes across the various groups.

Harmonization activities upon data ingest. When considering the data submission process, it is critical to understand the methods and processes by which data are mapped to a data model. Each node will be ultimately responsible for assuring adherence of data stored to a harmonized model. Although a fully-harmonized consensus data model across all of the nodes and data resources is preferred, it is possible that some nodes and data stakeholders will adhere to an internal model specific to that node's domain. In certain instances, the node or data resource will spend significant resources on data harmonization for the incoming data. This model is extremely unlikely to scale or be sustainable as the amounts of data grow.

Figure 3. Overview of “how does data get into CRDC nodes?”

Below, in **Table 1**, are details on how each node manages the ingest process - along with information about the nodes' harmonization procedures. Across the nodes and data resources, there are many opportunities to bring these various procedures and processes into alignment, as described in the section on recommendations.

Table 1. Data mapping and submission (submitter and node activities). Yellow indicates missing or yet to be collected information.

Data Mapping and Submission Process (how data are mapped to the node model)	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS
Data model templates with data elements available?	Yes (TSV and JSON formatted files)	Yes	No	No	N/A
Raw files may be submitted	Yes; FASTQ, BAM	Yes		N/A (comes from TCIA)	Yes
Submitter activities					
Submitter maps their data to node data format	Yes	Yes	(process is evolving)	N/A (comes from TCIA)	N/A (maybe in the future)
Submitter loads mapped data files	Yes (via Data Portal or API)	Yes (upload files via portal)		N	
Validation tool/wizard made available to users to do preliminary harmonization?	Yes			N/A	
Submission method by different types of data	See screenshot on 2nd tab			N/A	
Node activities					
Harmonization process overview (details about the data submission process for each node can be found on the CRDC Data Submission Landscape Analysis document)	A 2-check validation process. First, a validation process for the submitter, then, an internal process that completes mapping & transformation to match GDC's data model.			Clinical elements & data coming from source data (i.e., TCGA). Images are transformed to DICOM.* No clinical data annotation / harmonization process currently exists. Internally - synchronizing their 3 data sources with Google Cloud Healthcare API	
Processing that occurs during harmonization	GDC has 3 main processing activities that compose "harmonization": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● genomic data processing ● biospecimen data standardization ● clinical data standardization Code published here	Mass Spectrometry data. CDAP tool for harmonization to a standard.			
Does the node use a tool to map the structured clinical/ administrative data?	No	No	No	N/A	N/A
If yes, what mapping tool(s) are used?	Clinical data: None Genomics data: GDC Harmonization Pipeline .		Custom program	Custom API (TCIA to IDC)	N/A
Are new data elements added to the model before or after submission?	Before	Before	After	Before	Before
	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS

2.2 Quality Assurance / Quality Control

Building a transparent and auditable quality assurance / quality control (QA/QC) program is essential for any data provider. The approach to data quality control for each node and data stakeholder is outlined below (**Table 2**). Opportunities for developing new processes and aligning efforts across the CRDC are detailed in the section on recommendations. The information originates from interviews held with each of the nodes and public documentation.

Table 2. Node QA/QC processes.

QA/QC	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS
Does the node have a QA/QC program plan?	Yes	Yes (need to confirm)	?	N/A at this time	Not called out in SOP or flow process
Does the node validate adherence to a data dictionary for submissions?	Yes (submission template and validation)	Yes (submission template and assumed validation). Offers to help submitters if trouble matching fields.	N/A (the node maps metadata for the submitter)	N/A (data obtained via TCIA; clinical data model is pending)	N/A (Currently defining a minimum metadata set and a data model)
Does the node validate the file metadata for submissions?	Yes	Yes (need to confirm)	? The node offers personalized assistance to submitters. Confirm whether there is a formal, automated QA/QC process.	N/A (data obtained via TCIA)	No (dbGAP metadata stored in SRA; no further processing of metadata from specific NCI Program studies that do not use dbGAP.)

2.3 Mapping, transformation, harmonization

Perhaps no other set of processes are more critical for ensuring data interoperability than data mapping, transformation, and harmonization. Any high-quality data resource will have rigorous and repeatable processes in place for ETL (“extract, transform, load”) - the steps by which data are taken from source systems, mapped and aligned to a standard, and aggregated with existing data. Considerable expense is usually dedicated to these activities, as they are critical to downstream interoperability.

Metadata are the “data about the data.” For example, given a blood pressure reading of 120/80 mmHg, metadata about this measurement would be details about how this measurement was taken—the arm, the date and time, the method (manual vs. automatic), the person doing the measurement, etc.

Mapping the metadata means extracting these data and aligning them with elements in the data model. Continuing with the above example, there might be a field in the model for “site of measurement” and another field for “method.” The metadata mapping exercise would be associating the field in the metadata (for instance, “location”) with the metadata element in the model (e.g., “site”). Hopefully, these metadata elements will already be aligned—or will align with relative ease—but in some cases, this can be a tedious exercise. For instance, the measurement might be recorded as a text string and have to be parsed out (“120/80 mmHg in the right arm on 3/1/2021”).

Data mapping and transformation, on the other hand, is the process by which the actual measurements are aligned and harmonized together. While the target data model might have separate fields for systolic and

diastolic blood pressure, each measured in mmHg, the data source might have a combined field for blood pressure (e.g., 120/80 mmHg), and the measurements might not be in the correct units and would need to be transformed to a common unit (e.g., 16/11 kPa). Here, the values need to be parsed and converted before entry into the target data model (e.g., “16/11 kPa” → “120”, “80”).

Taken together, the processes of mapping and transforming metadata and data can be tedious and error-prone. A dedicated data standards expert or data scientist is best suited for this work—and ideally many of these tasks will be completed by the source data team prior to submission. As a final summary example, consider this blood pressure measurement:

<u>Source</u>	<u>Target</u>
Value: 16/11 kPa	Value: 120/80 mmHg
Site: Right upper arm	Location: Arm
Date: 3/1/2021 at 3:30pm CST	Laterality: Right
	Epoch timestamp: 1614634200

Below, these processes are described in more detail, and information about each node and data source’s approach to these activities are outlined. Opportunities for better alignment with best practices are offered in the section on recommendations.

While it is potentially useful to discuss these distinctions between data and metadata, they are inevitably going to be arbitrary—there is not always a clean distinction to be drawn between metadata and data that is not context dependent. There are data elements at the source that must be mapped to data elements in the target, and grouping these into metadata / data bins may seem arbitrary. A single source element may need to be deconstructed into multiple target elements if the target records the same concept in a more normalized form (as in the example above for blood pressure). Conversely, multiple source elements may need to be combined into a single target element if the source is more normalized than the destination. Nevertheless, drawing a distinction between these types of data can be useful and the examples given remain relevant and illustrative.

An example of this ambiguity is seen in the following scenario: When genomic data from research subjects are submitted to the Genomic Data Commons, those data are accompanied by clinical information of varying degrees of richness. These data may include the age, sex, race, ethnicity, diagnosis, and (hopefully) clinical outcome. While many might consider these values as “data,” for the purposes of cataloging and storing the genomic information, these clinical data are often thought of as metadata. And if one assumes that the definition of metadata is “data about the data,” this relationship holds. So, parsing out the distinctions is an illustrative academic exercise, but ultimately, what matters is that source elements must get mapped to elements in the target data model for any given node’s specific data modality. Extracting this information for each node’s needs for computational use with full identifier provenance while simultaneously maintaining the richness of the full clinical data is one of CRDC’s largest challenges.

Another important consequence of the current distributed model is that data are sometimes transformed multiple times, where the goal should be to minimize these transformations. For instance, data on the same subjects may be consumed by both the Proteomic Data Commons and the Genomic Data Commons. Each will perform its own mapping and harmonization of the data elements to fit their own model. Then when mapping to the CRDC-H data model (if in the context of compliant APIs, in CDA, cloud resources, etc.), those same data may end up being mapped differently.

Even if one model is derived from the other, there are still likely to be inconsistencies and customizations inherent to the local version of the model. What can result is that there are two different versions of the data that do not comply with a common model. When a second mapping to the harmonized CRDC data model is

performed, inconsistencies, ambiguities, or even errors may result from the multiple mappings. Consider the following theoretical example:

Site of disease = right cheek
Node A's model = Anatomic site = Cheek, right
Node B's model = Anatomic site = Face
Harmonized model - Although it has the granular element to account for right cheek, this information has been lost by Node B. So, the resulting harmonized data from Node A and Node B will be different, even though the source data were the same.

This example demonstrates one major problem—consistent / correct mappings to data models that are discordant. Another possible issue arises with inconsistent / incorrect mappings to models that are concordant, illustrated by the different definitions of the entity “*Project*” between the GDC and PDC.

These examples all indicate the strong need for a CRDC-wide harmonized process for data transformation using a centralized data model. One possible solution would be to have a centralized Data Coordination Center responsible for all data ingest, mapping, and transformation of data to a harmonized CRDC model. The DCC could house the clinical data and perform the identifier management, with subsequent data model compliant submission to each node only happening after the central DCC records are created. In this way, the nodes would perform the least amount of mapping and transformation possible, leaving these tasks to the centralized authority. Conversely, they would be responsible for the data type or domain specific modeling that they are solely responsible for, and can leverage in their own node specific analytics contexts.

2.3.1 Annotating data and metadata

As described above, it can be a useful academic exercise to discuss potential distinctions between data and metadata. Practically, making this distinction may not be that useful, since the same processes apply to all data—there are data elements at the source that must be mapped to data elements in the target. For the purposes of this discussion, the term “data” will be used throughout, though some might refer to the elements as metadata.

Thoughtful data annotation is essential to ensure that data are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). This is a critical step, often performed by the group receiving and storing the data (i.e., nodes and data resources), but this step can be greatly enhanced and facilitated by the submitter, given their knowledge of the data and its descriptors. The essential elements of data annotation include (1) creating an informative README, (2) assigning descriptive and standardized file names, (3) saving data in non-proprietary (open) formats, (4) providing citations and documentation for data provenance, and (5) assigning persistent identifiers for the dataset and derived resources (**Table 3**). Each node and stakeholder’s approach to data annotation is outlined below.

Table 3. How data annotation is performed by the nodes. File names may be at different levels for different nodes, where core administrative elements differ (e.g., the meaning of the word 'Case' differs between GDC and PDC). Yellow indicates missing or yet to be collected information.

Metadata Annotation	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS
Readme or equivalent	Yes Partial information at least, collected via Submission Template	Yes Partial information at least, collected via Submission Template	Yes Partial e.g., 'Index file was generated using samtools index command', 'WXS: FFPE prepared tumor tissue sample'	Yes Partial information; some available through explorer; basic metadata about image types, associated clinical or genomic data	n/a Some basic info through dbGAP metadata.
Descriptive File Names	Yes For Project Names No For File Names (which are UID identifiers - e.g., here)	Yes For study, project, program, and study ID, and ID (as left); Proteomics Data file IDs named as: (example: JX0030A_Colon_VU)	Yes For Case ID, Study Code, Sample ID; No For file names - based on source and data type, e.g. CCB010015.pdf, CGP-S01-4990-0F57044D-T6-A2-J01.aln.dup.realn.ecal.rp.bam	Yes For collection names, e.g., 'tcga_brca'; Users cannot see file names using the IDC browser. (However, source, e.g.TCGA file and DOI are linked.)	Uses dbGAP requirements.
Accepts open file formats	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes; but not clear what all the formats are/will be yet
Accepts some proprietary formats		Yes (e.g., Thermo RAW)		Yes (e.g., microscope)	
Accepted file format type (e.g., csv, bam, cram, etc.)	MAF (tab delimited text file), VCF, BAM, FASTQ, TXT, TSV, SVS, and others	TSV for clinical/admin, ".raw", ".d"; ".wiff"; ".wiff.scan"; ".wiff.mtd"; ".dat"; ".mis".for mass spectrometry files Extension descriptions here .	CSV for clinical/admin, BAM, FASTQ, pdf	Pathology: .svs, .tif, .vms, .vmu, .ndpi, .scn, .mrxs, .tif, .tiff, .svslide, .bif, .OMETif, .pillow, .geotiff, .netcdf Radiology: DICOM Clinical: JSON, XML, other easily convertible model format	Accept all submitter formats; FASTQ, BAM, CRAM, VCF, MAF Statistical data
Data provenance (do files including information about where the data comes from?)	Yes = some linked to dbGAP accession and addit'l metadata	Yes	Yes	? = all information is sourced from TCIA	Yes = some - linked to dbGAP accession and addit'l metadata
Dataset persistent ID¹	No (Uses UID)	No (UIDs for case, sample, study)	No (confirm)	Provides link to TCIA using the TCIA file DOI	N/A A data model is currently under development
Data license	not found here https://gdc.cancer.gov/about-gdc/gdc-policies ; report here: http://reusabledata.org/gdc.html	CC BY 4.0 found here: https://proteomic.datacommons.cancer.gov/pdc/data-use-guidelines	not found here: https://caninecommons.cancer.gov/#/icdc-data-model	not clear, likely multiple licenses from diff sources. See here: https://learn.canceridc.dev/data/organization-of-data	not clear, likely multiple licenses from diff sources. See here: https://datacommons.cancer.gov/repository/cancer-data-service
Metadata Annotation	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS

2.3.2 Mapping & Harmonization

As stated, mapping and harmonization can occur at several points during the data submission process. The submitters themselves may perform some degree of this work - and in most instances, they are indeed best suited for this task, given their deep domain knowledge as well as insights into the data itself. Providing submitters with sufficient resources (information, tools, QC reporting, and help) to perform their own mapping and harmonization will be a critical factor in the ongoing success and sustainability of the CRDC. An overview of data submission and where the mapping happens is provided in **Fig. 4**.

Figure 4. Data mapping across the CRDC

In the current state, there is no centralized coordination of data mapping and harmonization. As seen in Figure 4, there are three modes of mapping structured data: (a) shared/distributed—submitter completes templates with data field names as column headers or portal forms, node completes mapping/ harmonization [GDC, PDC], (b) programmatic—mapping is coded into the APIs [IDC, CTDC], and (c) "white glove", i.e. node maps 100% [ICDC]. While these serve the function of bringing data into the ecosystem, they do so at the expense of lacking standardized processes and procedures. In addition, this level of service is not sustainable as the CRDC scales.

Table 4. Data & Metadata Harmonization within each node.

	GDC	PDC	ICDC	CTDC	IDC	CDS
Metadata Harmonization						
Data Model Design	Homegrown, with genomics standards	Homegrown Based on GDC and proteomics standards	Homegrown	Based on MATCH	Based on TCIA, DICOM	In process; based on GDC, PDC, etc., with assistance from CCDH
When is mapping done to CDEs, NCIt?	During the design of new data elements, terminology.	Use CDEs & NCIt (Published in Data Model and DD). SI team works with them mapping or creating CDEs, terminologies for new datasets as needed.	It is done last. NCIt only.	It was done as the last step. Has mapped all terminology for CTDC nodes, properties, and values. Link	Pending: It is not done yet. CCDH did mapping as a test.	In progress: Working on adding both CDEs, NCIt to the design.
Which <i>other</i> semantics are used?	Received in ICD-O (mapped to NCIt)	Proteomics Standards Initiative (PSI)	N/A	N/A	DICOM SNOMED (within DICOM)	N/A
Data Harmonization						
Scientific Data Harmonization Platform	Pipeline, using GRCH 38 reference genome (genomics data)	CDAP for mass spec data	N/A	?	Converts to DICOM format	No
Harmonize submitted clinical / biospecimen Data Dictionary (DD) & Values	Yes Submission Template, DD and Viewer, QA/QC of data including values.	Yes Done by node (but CPTAC metadata, a major source, done with SI help ahead).	Yes Clinical / Administrative is done by the node.	Yes Via ETL API (e.g., for MATCH).	No	N/A To date, they only take whole files.

2.4 Data Dictionary and Data Modeling

A well-annotated and comprehensive data dictionary is absolutely critical to foster faithful and consistent data mapping. No data should be ingested, mapped, or modeled until a data dictionary has been created and balloted. While this process can be tedious and time consuming, jumping ahead to mapping and modeling can have long-lasting deleterious consequences. Perhaps even worse is creating a customized “internal” data dictionary or one that has input only from a small group of stakeholders. A data dictionary is a written inventory or catalog of all of the data elements and their permissible fields, ideally mapped to an accepted ontology. This includes definitions, references, and permissible values—all necessary for achieving a meaningful representation of the data, providing conceptual and syntactic correctness and completeness. The CDC has some [guidance](#) on the process of “modeling.” Here is a digest of those steps, adapted for the concept of data dictionary creation. The critical steps are: (1) involve stakeholders in data dictionary creation, (2) involve multiple people in the process, (3) build the dictionary incrementally, (4) allow for dictionary review, (5) ensure that the dictionary is traceable back to functional requirements, and (6) keep a record of all assumptions, constraints, issues, and other items—both addressed and unaddressed. Examples of data dictionaries include the [NIH COVID-19 data warehouse data dictionary](#), [NASA’s Scientific and Technical Information Program’s data dictionary](#), and the [Pediatric Cancer Data Commons AML dictionary](#).

An important distinction needs to be made between a data dictionary and a data model. As described above, a data dictionary is the list of fields and permissible values, sometimes linked to an ontology or controlled vocabulary. A data model, however, is a computable representation of all of the data elements and their relationships, and can contain components of the dictionary in the form of linked fields and tables (e.g., the SQL database).

An important question for each node and data resource is: *what represents their data dictionary?* Is it a homegrown, internal dictionary? Or does the node use an existing data model (e.g., DICOM for the IDC)? Is the model represented graphically or in some other visual representation, which can be useful for studying the model and understanding the relationship between terms? The model should be open source and published, available to anyone who wants to study it or leverage it for other applications. Importantly, any dictionary should utilize standard terminologies and/or an existing ontology. It is important to note whether or not the node observes an [early binding or late binding strategy](#). Some of these questions are addressed below, in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Details on Data Dictionaries and Modeling within each node.

Node Data Model Features	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC	CDS
Does node have a data model	Yes	Yes	Yes	DICOM; clinical data model - pending/in progress	In progress
Basis for node data model	Homegrown GDC	GDC + homegrown PDC	Homegrown	DICOM TBD for clinical data	pending: GDC, PDC, etc.
Data Model visual representation	Yes GDC Data Model	Yes NCI-PDC:Dictionary	Yes ICDC Data and Model	No	No
Data dictionary published	Yes	Yes	No	N/A	No
NCI CDEs Used	Yes	Partial	Partial	N/A	In future / work in progress
NCI Thesaurus Terminology (C codes)	Yes	Partial	Partial	N/A	In future / work in progress

2.5 Search & Analysis

The heart of any data commons platform is the search and discovery functionality, including cohort search and discovery. Each node and data resource should provide the ability for users to perform a faceted search over the available data. Beyond the user-facing interface, it is also useful if an API or other endpoint is made available for automated queries. In addition to search and discovery, it is useful for users to have some ability to perform analysis over the data without having to download the information. Examples might include survival curves or plots showing demographic distributions. Obviously, the kinds of queries and analyses will depend on the data available. The cohort search and analytic capabilities for each node and data resource are outlined below.

The real power and utility of the CRDC will be realized with fully cross-CRDC queries and analytics. Currently, these queries are not feasible, given the disparate ways in which each node handles cohort search. Ultimately, it will be useful for users to be able to launch a query across multiple resources to understand what data are available. As an example, a researcher might be studying children with osteosarcoma and want to study data with the following characteristics - Clinical: Age < 15, non-metastatic, both survivors and non-survivors, with associated genomic data and imaging (both radiologic as well as histologic). Not only will this require search over several types of data, it requires a common identifier to link patient information and samples. In addition, the current state of federated clinical data with multiple models makes this type of query difficult. But as these

issues are resolved (see Recommendations), the CRDC will realize its mission as an incredibly powerful tool for search and discovery and for obtaining multiple kinds of disparate research data.

2.5.1 Node Portals

GDC, PDC, ICDC, and IDC have public portals, the key characteristics of which are described in **Table 6** below. CTDC and CDS have not yet created public portals. The look and feel of each existing public portal is different, though some have similar features.

Table 6: Summary of Portal Characteristics

Portal Features	GDC	PDC	ICDC	IDC
Faceting search by clinical data fields	Yes Filter by Cases, Clinical Data, Genes, Mutations	Yes Filter by General, Biospecimen, Clinical data, Files, Genes	Yes Filter by Cases, Programs, Studies	Yes Limited to image data. Filter by Collections, search configuration
Allow Data Browsing in Portal	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Search by API query	Yes	PDC GraphQL API, PDC Swagger API	?	?
Viewer Display Tools	None. Portal only	None. Portal only	None. Portal only	Image viewer & portal
Analysis Tools	Set Operations, Cohort Comparison, Clinical Data Analysis	Peptide Genome Mapping, PepQuery	None	N/A
Information about Data Use Guidelines	Yes	Yes	N/A	N/A only public TCIA collections for initial release
Link to Cloud Resources for analysis	Yes	None	Yes Preliminary	Yes For links to TCIA?
Export Manifest for use with Cloud Resources	Yes	Yes directions are on Seven Bridges website, not on PDC	Yes	?

2.5.2 Cloud Resources

One of the major benefits of a data commons is that data can be analyzed in a cloud-based infrastructure. For instance, a virtual machine can be launched with data automatically transferred into the VM. Commonly-used tools (e.g., R) can be made available for the user. In fact, this system can promote the sharing of workflows and tools between users and projects. These cloud-based systems for data delivery and analysis are still in the early stages of development but will become increasingly popular for researchers. As cross-node search and discovery becomes more popular and easier to accomplish, it will become even more important to provide users with a cloud-based system for disparate data aggregation and analysis. In the example above, it would be useful for the user to have a single cloud VM into which the different data types are deposited (clinical, genomic, imaging). Currently, the most common avenue for data delivery is for the researcher to directly download the information to their local system, where they have their own tools installed. Users who download data are subject to all of the rules and restrictions imposed during the project request phase.

In addition to launching the GDC in 2016, the NCI also launched [three Cancer Genomics Cloud Resources](#), tasked with standardizing data submission, ensuring data quality, harmonizing genomic datasets, and providing

users with secure access to data. Like the GDC, the three cloud resources (Broad Institute FireCloud, Institute for Systems Biology, and Seven Bridges Genomics) harness both Google Cloud Service and Amazon Web Services. By co-locating petabytes of GDC, PDC, and other data, the cloud resources can provide elastic compute power and further decrease the need for users to download the information locally. In fact, users have the ability to load their own customized pipelines into the cloud infrastructure.

Summaries of the CGC Resources are detailed below. Where possible, information is detailed on (1) data source(s), (2) access method, (3) processing and storage, (4) mapping and transformation, (5) data schema, (6) tools used, and (7) future plans.

2.5.2.1 FireCloud (Broad Institute / Terra)

Table 7a. Summary of Data Flow and Management for Broad Institute FireCloud / Terra Cloud Resources. Additional information can be found in Appendix B.1.

Broad Institute FireCloud / Terra		
Program/Data Source	GDC-TCGA, TARGET, etc. through Terra (new)	Existing TCGA and TARGET (FireCloud)
How to access	Terra: Users can browse a tabular version of datasets within workspaces, which include metadata tables that point to the external data files, usually via Data Repository Service (DRS) URIs.	FireCloud Dashboard (here)
Processing, Storage, Mapping & Transformation	<p>A copy of GDC datasets are statically housed within FireCloud.</p> <p>Steps: query data from the GDC portal, download the query manifest, edit query manifest to .tsv, upload .tsv file to workspace data table in Terra. Within a workspace, the data is aligned to a data model via the creation of data tables. Data is manually curated and updated from the GDC data.</p> <p>Currently working on tutorials for dynamic querying of data in GDC and PDC to create DRS manifests to upload into FireCloud to point at data. FireCloud can resolve the DRS URIs provided.</p>	<p>Metadata describing dataset workspaces on DASHBOARD is not identical to GDC's. E.g., TCGA: 'Primary Disease Site.'</p> <p>Value = Brain 'Primary Disease Site Brain ', therefore probably manually keyed, not a value set. (see screen shot).</p> <p>TARGET metadata is not identical, there is no field for 'Primary Disease Site'. Linkage of Patient to Clinical and Biospecimen through UUIDs.</p>
Schema	Generally utilizes the existing schema, but will often pivot data to make it more entity centric (e.g., <i>Samples</i> or <i>Participants</i> in studies) and less file centric.	
Tools	<p><i>Search</i>: APIs, Standard SQL</p> <p><i>Analysis</i>: custom; ok for users to bring their own</p> <p><i>Pre-processing</i>: custom</p> <p><i>For Users</i>: WDL workflows, notebooks (Jupyter, R), customizable</p> <p><i>Enabling semantics</i>: GUID to DRS URI transformations</p> <p><i>Mapping</i>: N/A</p>	
Future Plans	<p>Focus on expanding and solidifying interoperable access methodologies to nodes, specifically: DRS, RAS, and PFB.</p> <p>Implement CDA's ETL, allowing users to find data across nodes.</p>	
Notes	Access through <i>Terra</i> requires an account and credentials. Once GDC and Terra accounts are linked, workflow can be used to test access. This test should output a simple md5 sum if data access is set up properly, and fail otherwise.	HG38 TCGA and TARGET workspaces reference files by their GDC UUIDs. To run analyses on referenced data files, users need to run workflows that retrieve the files from GDC and copy them to their workspace bucket.

2.5.2.2. Cancer Genomics Cloud (Seven Bridges)

Table 7b. Summary of Data Flow and Management for Seven Bridges Cancer Genomics Cloud (SB-CGC). Additional information can be found in Appendix B.2.

Seven Bridges Cancer Genomics Cloud (SB-CGC)	
Program/Data Source	Interacts with Gen3 to index available data from GDC (TCGA, TARGET, CCLE, CPTAC-3, FM), PDC, ICDC, CDS. Public projects in the CGC which contain some open-access datasets, such as TCIA (Imaging), CPTAC (Proteomics), SGDP (Simons), HCIAPD (Human Cell Atlas).
How to access	Uses Gen3 as AuthN/Z and file content provider. Indexing: relies on APIs; true for GDC, PDC, ICDC, CDS. Fence and IndexD provide identifiers for files, currently a Gen3 GUID but moving to a DRS URI. ICGC data available through ICGC API (both indexing and AuthN/Z). To retrieve metadata, SB-CGC uses APIs from GDC, PDC, ICDC, ICGC, SRA. More info here . SB-CGC Data Browser
Processing, Storage, Mapping & Transformation	File level metadata is stored within the SB filesystem on the CGC. Each dataset available in Data Browser and Datasets API has its ontology. Metadata schema is defined on the platform level. Phenotype information is stored in a graph database. Creation or updating of a {entity, utility, property} map for each dataset to ensure it is compliant (resolve duplication or missing values, etc.)
Schema	There is an internal schema similar to the GDC schema. It allows users to search unions or intersects between the following datasets.
Tools	<i>Search:</i> Multiple cohort builders: Data Overview, Case Explorer, Data Browser, support flows for exploration and cohort formation at external Data Portals. <i>Analysis:</i> Over 500 commonly used bioinformatics tools available as Public Apps <i>Pre-processing:</i> Yes, included in the collection mentioned above. <i>For Users:</i> Yes, included in the collection mentioned above. <i>Enabling semantics:</i> N/A <i>Mapping:</i> N/A
Future Plans	Actively testing the CDA release v1
Notes	Requires an account to access the data browser.

2.5.2.3 Institute for Systems Biology Cancer Gateway in the Cloud (ISB-CGC)

Table 7c. Summaries of Data Flow and Management for Institute for Systems Biology Cancer Gateway in the Cloud (ISB-CGC). Additional information can be found in Appendix B.3.

Institute for Systems Biology Cancer Gateway in the Cloud (ISB-CGC)						
Program/Data Source	GDC, PDC, UniProt, COSMIC, GENCODE, Pan Cancer Atlas, Mitelman Database of Chromosome Aberrations and Gene Fusions in Cancer, Other Reference and Annotation datasets.					
	The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA): GDC-TCGA, Therapeutically Applicable Research To Generate Effective Treatments (TARGET), Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia (CCLE), etc.			Clinical Proteomic Tumor Analysis Consortium (CPTAC): GDC-CPTAC, PDC-CPTAC	ICPC (data from PDC)	GTEX
How to access	Google Cloud Storage (GCS) Buckets & Tools	BigQuery Tables	Cohort Builder web application	BigQuery Tables		
Processing, Storage, Mapping & Transformation	GCS: All individual processed data files are accessible through GDC Google Cloud Storage buckets; ISB-CGC provides pointers to these files.	Google BigQuery: Processed data are consolidated by data type (eg. Clinical, DNA Methylation, RNAseq, Somatic Mutation) and transformed into ISB-CGC Google BigQuery tables for ease of access and analysis.	(Appears to use) GDC metadata for stratification/search	From GDC	Includes clinical data and protein expression data files	From GTEX portal, has its own metadata file avail – (not CRDC)
Schema	It varies: some come directly from the data source and ISB-CGC can add field descriptions. In some cases, schema mapping data is incomplete (missing descriptions) or data type definitions don't map directly with BigQuery, so these are inferred programmatically or manually supplied via a json file.					
Tools	<p><i>Search:</i> Cohort builder, BigQuery project direct access, BigQuery table search interface, Data access using Google Cloud tools</p> <p><i>Analysis, Pre-processing, For Users:</i> ISB-CGC allows users to work in their own Google Cloud projects using whatever tools or workflows they choose on their own VMs. It leans heavily on employing Google BigQuery to allow users to explore the CRDC data hosted in BigQuery tables.</p> <p><i>Enabling semantics:</i> manipulating the data to some extent--combining data from multiple endpoints, incorporating external mapping sources to occasionally augment the imported data, creating project-level or study-level tables which filter out all-null columns and flatten extraneous nesting</p> <p><i>Mapping:</i> Users need to map their own metadata semantics onto what ISB-CGC provides.</p>					
Future Plans	Plans to expand the listing of files are associated with a given cohort to include associated BigQuery tables. Integration of more sources and incorporation of new sources (IDC, CDA, etc.) Generic ETL tools for automation.					
Notes	Data hosted by GDC is contained in Google Cloud Storage (GCS). Metadata stored within ISB-CGC BigQuery tables contains pointers to file locations in these GDC data. Also stores genome reference sources (e.g. GENCODE, miRBase, and ICD codes, GO, etc.) CPTAC supplies clinical data and proteomic experimental data for CPTAC cases, GDC supplies genomics data for CPTAC cases.					

2.6 CRDC Change Management for data models, terminologies, and tools

Change management is an important feature for any data warehouse or platform. Even the most stable data dictionaries and models are subject to modification as the science advances and as needs change. A data model must be built with the flexibility to allow for additions, though modifications and deletions will always be challenging. For instance, adding in a new genomic finding or alteration should be a trivial operation. However, deleting a finding or creating a new one that includes existing data is a difficult task. As an example, considering the genetic findings in neuroblastoma of MYCN amplification, 10p deletion, and 17q gain. After several years of stability, the International Neuroblastoma Risk Group requests the addition of ALK gene modifications to the data dictionary. This change will not fundamentally alter the data model, but requires the addition of a new term to the NCI or other terminology, and this modification should be tracked and be auditable.

The following discussion can apply to data dictionary change, model modifications, and tool development. While there will be differences in execution and stakeholder involvement, the same principles apply across all domains. In addition to requesting changes to the dictionary, model or tools, users may even request changes to existing data. In fact, the Pediatric Cancer Data Commons receives updated outcome information from the Children's Oncology Group every six months, requiring an auditable process for keeping track of any updated information.

In considering any change, the following criteria may be useful:

- *Implementation* - What is the level of effort? What kinds of technical resources are needed? What are the costs?
- *Value* - Will the change improve usability? Is it a fix? What is the value to the user base and/or the organization?
- *Special considerations* - Are there impacts on security?

Of note, like many types of technical specification gathering, understanding change requests can be challenging. The data node or resource should be prepared to spend sufficient time gathering the information from the user in order to completely understand the change being requested and any downstream implications of making the change. It is advisable that proposed changes go through a governance process during which cross-CRDC leadership can have insight into larger changes and how they may affect the overall CRDC ecosystem.

2.7 CCDH Harmonized data model (CRDC-H) Change Management

Of particular importance to the success of the CRDC is the harmonized model being developed by the CCDH. The CRDC harmonized data model (CRDC-H) is being built as a generalized data dictionary and accompanying data model that covers the most important elements across the CRDC (e.g., demographics, specimen information with clinical information to follow soon). Of course, each node and data resource will need access to customized extensions of the data model for their particular unique areas. But with a harmonized set of elements across the CRDC, a minimal set of data can be cross-harmonized.

5. Acknowledgements

Our most sincere gratitude goes to the very kind and generous members of the following teams:

Cancer Data Aggregator (CDA)

Genomics Data Commons (GDC)

Imaging Data Commons (IDC)

Cancer Data Service (CDS)

Protein Data Commons (PDC)

Integrated Canine Data Commons (ICDC)

Seven Bridges Cancer Genomic Cloud (SB-CGC)

Institute for Systems Biology Cancer Gateway in the Cloud (ISB-CGC)

FireCloud (Broad Institute / Terra)

NCI / FNL Federal Oversight Team to the CCDH

CCDH Team

6. APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Nodes' Data Lifecycle - Current Status

Figure A.1. Genomics Data Commons (GDC) Data Lifecycle.

Figure A.2. Imaging Data Commons (IDC) Data Lifecycle.

Figure A.3. Cancer Data Service (CDS) Data Lifecycle.

PDC - Data Lifecycle - Submission to Analysis

Figure A.4. Proteomics Data Commons (PDC) Data Lifecycle.

ICDC - Data Lifecycle - Submission to Analysis

Figure A.5. Integrated Canine Data Commons (ICDC) Data Lifecycle.

APPENDIX B: Narrative Documentation from the Cloud Resources

B.1 FireCloud (Broad Institute / Terra)

1. *Where do you get your data from, and how? E.g., Ingest? Linking (e.g., via identifiers)? Please provide as much detail as you'd like.*
 - a. A copy of GDC datasets are statically housed within FireCloud. Researchers browse for the dataset of interest via a cohort browser within the platform. Researchers select the dataset of interest and the data is pointed to a workspace, where it can be analyzed with other data(sets). Within a workspace, the data is aligned to a data model via the creation of data tables. Data is manually curated and updated from the GDC data
 - b. Currently working on tutorials for dynamic querying of data in GDC and PDC to create DRS manifests to upload into FireCloud to point at data. FireCloud can resolve the DRS URIs provided.
2. *What data are you storing internally? E.g., Clinical and biospecimen data and metadata, file metadata, project metadata*
 - a. We store clinical and biospecimen data file pointers (to Google bucket files), and the associated metadata. In general, we do not store the file metadata or project metadata.
3. *How are you processing the data to enable searching?*
 - a. *For example, what do you do with the data and/or metadata to prepare them for public access?*
 - i. We typically perform some transformations on the data to make it more entity centric (e.g. Samples or Participants in studies) and less file centric. Our tools are set up and intended to have sets of files associated with entities - e.g. a given Sample may have a BAM, BAI, VCF, and TBI file pointer as an attribute (column) for that given Sample row.
 - b. *Is there an internal schema? Or do you use the schema(s) directly from the source?*
 - i. We generally utilize the existing schema, but will often pivot the data to the shape as described in (a) above.
4. *How do you enable browsing? (include details about browsing engine, back-end architecture as possible)*
 - a. *Buckets vs. BigQuery tables vs. cohort builders/ browsers*
 - i. Users can browse a tabular version of datasets within workspaces, which include metadata tables that point to the external data files, usually via DRS URIs. We do not usually provide cohort builders for these external datasets, as many of them have their own portals for cohort building and we don't see the value in duplicating the work. For instance, with NHLBI's BioData Catalyst, a user can find a cohort there, and export that metadata to Terra. That process then populates the metadata table with the clinical and file metadata for that given cohort.
 - b. *What is the 'current state' at your resources?*
 - i. We have focused recently on ways to support "handing off" data from a given portal/cohort builder into Terra, which means we can get data that is as up to date as that portal into Terra as needed by the user. Some of our other data is not as up to date as we would like it to be.
 - c. *What do future plans look like?*
 - i. We are working on ingesting more data into our Data Repository, which provides extensive querying and cohort building capabilities, and rich transformation capabilities using Standard SQL. We also plan to expand more of our "hand off" mechanisms where ever possible. We would like to focus on more interoperable means of connecting to or handing off data from multiple data sources, or make use of aggregation tools that can search across multiple data sources, similar to what the Cancer Data Aggregator is working towards.
5. *What tools are you using? And what tools do users have access to today? Please clarify whether existing or planned, where applicable.*

- a. *Search tools*
 - i. APIs to retrieve and filter workspace metadata, and APIs and Standard SQL via our Data Repository. Also working on generic cohort builder UIs for the Data Repository.
 - b. *Analysis tools*
 - i. *Do you use your own tools? Google tools? Other sources?*
 - 1. We build our own analysis tools (GATK best practice tools), and allow users to bring in their own tools as they need as well.
 - c. *Pre-processing Tools, algorithms*
 - i. For data ingestion and harmonization, we have tooling we have built to scale up to large datasets.
 - d. *Tools for Users, how do users access algorithms*
 - i. Users are able to access existing WDL workflows, build their own WDL workflows, and make use of notebook functionality (e.g. Jupyter and RStudio) both via existing notebook content or by writing their own.
 - e. *Tools to enable/support semantics mapping*
 - i. *E.g., are you processing clinical metadata, assigning your own tags, or using as is from the nodes?*
 - 1. We do not change any of the data from nodes, but sometimes do pivots or some transformations (e.g. from GUIDs to DRS URIs) to support interoperability with tools within our platform.
 - ii. *Are there tools to support users who bring their own data to combine their semantics metadata, i.e., mapping tools or services?*
 - 1. At the moment, we do not provide users tools for this, but many users do this via notebooks.
6. *What else is important for us to know about the architecture vis-a-vis describing the flow of data from submission through analysis in the data lifecycle?*
- a. *What is being done today? What is planned for the next 6 - 12 months?*
 - i. Today and for the next 6-12 months we plan to focus on expanding and solidifying our interoperable access methodologies to nodes, specifically: DRS, RAS (for login and data access), and PFB (for handing off metadata from a node to our platform). We also will be further incorporating our Data Repository into Terra so that users can better query that metadata via Standard SQL.
 - b. *E.g., any plans/ideas about how to use CDA to facilitate searching?*
 - i. There are several challenges for users now when accessing data - some of which we have made easier via standards like DRS and the work on RAS, but others of which are still gaps, such as the lack of harmonization across datasets. The CDA will allow our users to find data, regardless of which NCI node it comes from, and the fact that that data will be more harmonized/standardized means that we can write generic tooling to transform that data to be actionable within our platform - meaning that a user can run an existing workflow or notebook on the data with little configuration needed.

B.2 Seven Bridges Cancer Genomics Cloud (SB-CGC)

- 1. *Where do you get your data from, and how? E.g., Ingest? Linking (e.g., via identifiers)? Please provide as much detail as you'd like.*
 - a. Seven Bridges (SB) interacts with Gen3 to index available data on the GDC (TCGA, TARGET, CCLE, CPTAC-3, FM), PDC, ICDC, CDS. There are public projects in the CGC which contain some open-access datasets, such as TCIA (Imaging), CPTAC (Proteomics), SGDP (Simons), HCellAtlas (Human Cell Atlas). Gen3 is serving mainly as AuthN/Z and file content provider. For indexing, we usually rely on some "more relevant" APIs - for example, for indexing GDC datasets we use the GDC API, not Gen3. It's the same for other datasets: PDC, ICDC, CDS (for

CDS we use SRA). Fence and IndexD provide identifiers for the files, currently a Gen3 GUID but moving to a DRS URI. ICGC data is also made available. We used ICGC API both for indexing and for AuthN/Z.

Additionally, for getting metadata, we use the APIs from GDC, PDC, ICDC, ICGC, SRA. It also contains file names and types, so it's the "first point of contact". At the moment when we index files in our file system, we contact Gen3 IndexD (based on Gen3 UUID information we get from some non-Gen3 API or manifest), check if file exists, and from IndexD we take only size of the file which we also associate with file in our file system as a file attribute (or system metadata). The phenotype/clinical/demographic (hereafter simplified to phenotype) data is indexed directly from the GDC or other data portal APIs. For each file available in Gen3, we pre-index all available phenotype data (e.g. case_id, experimental design, sequencing tech, age, treatment). Pre-indexing is done to ensure that SB users will have performant search from within the CGC. Additionally, both file-level metadata and phenotype are leveraged by analysis pipelines and tools (e.g. family_id to group trios, sample_type for diff exp).

2. *What data are you storing internally? E.g., Clinical and biospecimen data and metadata, file metadata, project metadata.*

- a. File level metadata is stored within the SB filesystem on the CGC. Each dataset in the file system has its metadata schema - it consists of metadata fields which are associated with each dataset file. Also, each dataset available in Data Browser and Datasets API has its ontology, which represents how the data is structured within the dataset. Finally, there's metadata schema defined on the platform level, and it's described here:
<https://docs.cancer-genomics-cloud.org/docs/metadata-for-private-data>.

The phenotype information is stored in a graph database to enable exploration and cohort creation (see Question 3). When users create a cohort within the Data Browser in the CGC using the phenotype or genotype metadata, the result of a cohort is a set of files that fall within the criteria used for cohort creation. An interesting application of this feature is the ability to find proteomic and genomic files at the same time. It can also be exported as a table for further analysis on the CGC (e.g. Survival Analysis, GWAS).

3. *How are you processing the data to enable searching?*

- a. *For example, what do you do with the data and/or metadata to prepare them for public access?*
 - i. Data ingress and integration is managed by the Data Exploration and Visualization (DEV) Team within our engineering department. There is a process including creation or updating of a {entity, utility, property} map for each dataset to ensure it is compliant. Issues such as duplication or missing values may be resolved here. For highly-used and/or complex datasets (e.g. TCGA), the DEV team may restructure or optimize the {entity, utility, property} map such that search will be performant.
- b. *Is there an internal schema? Or do you use the schema(s) directly from the source?*
 - i. Yes, there is an internal schema similar to the GDC schema. It allows users to search unions or intersects between the following datasets.

Featured datasets ^
 Featured datasets to explore [Learn More](#)

- TCGA GRCh38**
 GDC v28 · DM 2021.2.0 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- TARGET GRCh38**
 GDC v28 · DM 2020.11.0 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- CPTAC**
 DM 2020.8.0 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- CPTAC-3**
 GDC v28 · DM 2021.2.1 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- TCIA**
 DM 2020.8.0 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- ICGC**
 DM 2020.8.0 ⓘ [Details](#) v
- FM**
 GDC v28 · DM 2021.3.1 ⓘ [Details](#) v

4. How do you enable browsing? (include details about browsing engine, back-end architecture as possible)

a. Buckets vs. BigQuery tables vs. cohort builders/ browsers

i. Multiple cohort builders. These are connected to a performant triple-store (currently Blazegraph). Currently SB includes multiple tools to explore and analyze the data.

Data Overview (<https://cgc.sbggenomics.com/datasets/#/data-overview>) helps users search datasets to understand the overall structure (e.g., summary stats) of a particular dataset. Find more info about the Data Overview here:

<https://docs.cancer-genomics-cloud.org/docs/about-the-data-overview>

Case Explorer (<https://cgc.sbgenomics.com/datasets/#/tcga/case-explorer>) provides a way to further refine a cohort based on molecular information. Find more information about the Case Explorer at <https://docs.cancergenomicscloud.org/docs/about-the-case-explorer>

Data Browser (<https://cgc.sbgenomics.com/datasets/#/data-browser>) is our primary search portal, allowing users to form cohorts based on file metadata and phenotype. For example below we have a query for cases with matched tumor-normal samples processed with WGS. From here, users can directly create a pointer to the underlying source files (here bam) in a CGC Project for further collaborative analysis. Additional details about the Data Browser can be found here: <https://docs.cancergenomicscloud.org/docs/about-the-data-browser>

The screenshot displays the TCGA Data Portal interface for a WGS BAM file. The top navigation bar includes 'TCGA', 'Projects', 'Data', 'Public Apps', 'Public projects', 'Developer', and 'Staff'. The main header shows the project name 'WGS BAM files from Thyroid Carcinoma cases, produced from tumor/matched normal sample type' and options like 'Create new query', 'Queries', 'Search by ID', and 'Copy files to project'. The central part of the interface shows a hierarchical tree view with nodes for Case, Sample, and File. The 'File 1' node is selected and expanded, showing its details in a table below. The 'Connections' panel on the right shows the file's inbound and outbound connections.

TCGA	
Diagnosis	
Disease type	Thyroid Carcinoma
Access level	Controlled
Data format	BAM
Data submitting center	Harvard Medical School
Data subtype	Aligned Reads

Finally, we support flows where users do exploration and cohort formation at external Data Portals, e.g., PDC. Here we can import the manifest produced by the external portal. Documentation pages for importing manifest files from different data nodes: [Import data from the PDC](#), [Import data from ICDC](#), and [Import CDS data](#).

The screenshot shows the 'Add files to "new project"' interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Case Explorer and Data Browser', 'Public Files', 'Projects', 'Your Computer', 'FTP / HTTP', 'Data Tools', 'Volumes', and 'Import from a manifest file'. Below this, there is a section for 'Import files from' with a dropdown menu set to 'Proteomic Data Commons (PDC)'. A text box prompts the user to 'Upload a .csv manifest file previously generated on the PDC website' and provides a link for 'available releases of PDC data on the CGC'. A 'Select file' button shows 'No file chosen'. A warning message states: 'Some NCI data are under an EMBARGO for publication and/or citation. For more details, visit the NCI Proteomic Data Commons for the study of interest.' An 'Import' button is located at the bottom right.

- b. What is the 'current state' at your resources?
 - i. Production-grade.
- c. What do future plans look like?

- a. GDC and PDC API requests. Responses are ingested into intermediate bigquery tables in their native form (nested, etc), then flattened/mutated/combined as needed
 - b. GDC GCS buckets
 - c. COSMIC AWS buckets
2. *What data are you storing internally? E.g., Clinical and biospecimen data and metadata, file metadata, project metadata.*
- GDC
 - Clinical biospecimen data (per-project tables)
 - Case and file metadata
 - Aliquot to case mapping table
 - File to GCS url
 - Slide to case mapping table
 - Per sample file metadata
 - Derived data
 - mRNA seq
 - miRNA seq
 - Isoform miRNA seq
 - Somatic Mutation
 - Copy Number Variation
 - Methylation
 - Slide and Radiology Images
 - PDC
 - Program/project/study metadata
 - Clinical biospecimen data (per-project tables)
 - Case and file metadata (currently only master tables have been created, but will also include either per-project or per-study tables)
 - Quant data matrix derived data (protein abundance log₂_ratio, stored in per-study tables)
 - Case-sample-aliquot mapping table
 - Case external mapping tables--internal case uuid to external program case uuid (GDC, TCIA, etc)
 - UniProt
 - UniProt gene identifier mapping data
 - Swiss-Prot protein accession numbers
 - These tables are used internally in the quant data matrix ETL process--consulting bioinformatician noted that Swiss-Prot is the modern "industry standard" for mapping gene to protein sequence
 - COSMIC
 - All CSV and TSV files
 - GENCODE
 - Version 19 and 22 used in GDC derived data ETL process though we offer other more current versions also
 - Pan Cancer Atlas
 - Files shared by the PanCancer Atlas initiative
 - Mitelman Database of Chromosome Aberrations and Gene Fusions in Cancer
 - Other Reference and Annotation datasets
3. *How are you processing the data to enable searching?*
- a. *For example, what do you do with the data and/or metadata to prepare them for public access?*
 - i. Some table data normalization in order to create better filtering
 - ii. BQ table metadata identifying the data contained in the table

1. description including source, month/year ingested
 2. labels indicating open/controlled access, data source, status (current/archived), category, data type, associated program
 - iii. Concatenation of derived data files into a single table
 - iv. Instead of hitting data commons APIs, users can access, explore and search much of the data available at the GDC and PDC through our BigQuery tables.
- b. *Is there an internal schema? Or do you use the schema(s) directly from the source?*
- i. For some workflows, schemas come directly from the data source. On our end, we add field descriptions to schemas where fields are described at the source.
 - ii. In some cases, schema mapping data is incomplete (for instance, missing descriptions) or data type definitions don't map directly with BigQuery, so these are inferred programmatically or manually supplied via a json file.
4. *How do you enable browsing? (include details about browsing engine, back-end architecture as possible)*
- a. *Buckets vs. BigQuery tables vs. cohort builders/ browsers*
 - i. *Cohort builder*
 - ii. *BigQuery project direct access*
 - iii. *BigQuery table search interface*
 - iv. *Data access using Google Cloud tools*
 - b. *What is the 'current state' at your resources?*
 - i. Items described in the above list are all currently available
 - c. *What do future plans look like?*
 - i. Our current plans are to expand the listing of files that are associated with a given cohort to also include associated BigQuery tables.
5. *What tools are you using? And what tools do users have access to today? Please clarify whether existing or planned, where applicable.*

NOTE from the CR: This question is somewhat unclear. Are you referring to tools we use to do our data ETL processes, or the **tools available to researchers when using our Resource to do research**? We assume the latter.

- a. *Search tools*
 - i. See 4a above.
- b. *Analysis tools*
 - i. *Do you use your own tools? Google tools? Other sources?*
 1. ISB-CGC is designed to allow users to work in their own Google Cloud projects, and use whatever tools or workflows they choose on their own VMs.
 2. ISB-CGC does lean heavily on employing Google BigQuery to allow users to explore the CRDC data hosted in BigQuery tables.
- c. *Pre-processing Tools, algorithms*
 - i. See 5bi above
- d. *Tools for Users, how do users access algorithms*
 - i. See 5bi above
- e. *Tools to enable/support semantics mapping*
 - i. *E.g., are you processing clinical metadata, assigning your own tags, or using as is from the nodes?*
 1. Generally we are manipulating the data to some extent--combining data from multiple endpoints, incorporating external mapping sources to occasionally augment the imported data, creating project-level or study-level tables which filter out all-null columns and flatten extraneous nesting

- a. This serves both our public-facing BQ tables and provides slightly modified versions for Solr ingestion
 - b. We are not working to try to harmonize data models between different nodes or different programs offered by a node, but are passing through the attributes and values as provided by the nodes.
- ii. *Are there tools to support users who bring their own data to combine their semantics metadata, i.e., mapping tools or services?*
- 1. Users need to map their own metadata semantics onto what ISB-CGC provides, which is mostly a pass-through of the models provided by the data nodes.
6. *What else is important for us to know about the architecture vis-a-vis describing the flow of data from submission through analysis in the data lifecycle?*
- a. *What is being done today? What is planned for the next 6 - 12 months?*
 - i. *Integration of more data from existing sources, and incorporation of new sources (IDC, CDA, etc.)*
 - ii. *We're also working on generic ETL tools which automate parts of our process, and will publish them as public python packages*
 - b. *E.g., any plans/ideas about how to use CDA to facilitate searching?*
 - i. We have not delved deeply into planning this yet.